

THE DETERMINATION OF THE PARACHORS OF INORGANIC
SALTS IN SOLUTIONS. PART III. THE PARACHORS
OF SOME SALTS OF MAGNESIUM, STRONTIUM
AND BARIUM, AND THE ATOMIC PARA-
CHOR OF THE ABOVE ELEMENTS
AND RADIUM.

BY JAMIAT V. LAKHANI AND RUSTOM P. DAROGA.

The "solution method" of measuring parachor has been extended to determine experimentally the parachors of some Mg, Sr and Ba salts, not previously done. The atomic parachor of Mg and Sr (previously not known) has been computed from the data of the salts. The log atomic number—log parachor relationship has been found to hold in the case of group II metals also and a straight line curve is obtained. The atomic parachor of radium from the above relationship is deduced to be 140.

The object of the present investigation has been to ascertain whether the log atomic number—log parachor relationship that has been established by the authors in the case of the alkali metals (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 519) would also hold in the case of alkaline earth metals (Be, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba) and if so to deduce therefrom the atomic parachor of radium, which belongs to the same group of elements but whose parachor cannot be determined on account of the high cost and rarity of the metal and its salts. The parachor of beryllium and calcium has been known by the fusion method with a degree of certainty (Sugden, "Parachor and Valency" pp. 145, 187) but that of magnesium, strontium and barium atoms has not been calculated or experimentally established. In consequence of this, the parachors of some soluble salts of magnesium, strontium and barium have been determined by the "solution method" (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 37) and the atomic parachors of the above metals have been deduced from the parachors of the salts. This deduction is based on the fact pointed out by the authors (*loc. cit.*) that the parachor is invariably found to maintain its additive character in the case of simple inorganic salts.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All measurements of surface tensions have been carried out at 30±'02° by the capillary rise method and the apparatus and other experimental details were exactly the same as already described (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 37).

In the table below are given the data and the results obtained with three magnesium salts, three strontium salts, and two barium salts.

TABLE I.

Magnesium, strontium and barium salts.

Substance.	X.	D.	V.	M _m .	P _m .	P _x (parachor observed).	[P] without metal.	Parachor of the metal deduced from the observed value of the salt.
MgCl ₂ , 6H ₂ O (temp., 30.2°)	0.03117 0.03634	1.125 1.144	83.43 84.14	20.408 20.811	54.84 55.08	161.7 163.5 (mean 162.6)		Mg = 57.2
Mg(NO ₃) ₂ , 6H ₂ O (temp., 35°)	0.02283 0.02379	1.129 1.133	79.50 79.58	20.977 21.098	55.49 55.55	238.2 238.8 (mean 238.5)		Mg = 56.7
MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O (temp., 35°)	0.02082	1.128	77.56	20.135	52.95	177.62		Mg = 59.12 (mean 57.7)
SrCl ₂ , 6H ₂ O	0.02273 0.02732	1.165 1.199	82.85 84.31	21.194 21.843	54.91 55.18	188.34 193.98 (mean 191.161)	105.4	85.76
SrBr ₂ , 6H ₂ O	0.03004 0.03157	1.335 1.351	79.00 79.12	24.893 25.251	55.59 55.75	214.4 218.4 (mean 216.4)	132.8	83.6
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	0.03292	1.271	75.96	24.375	56.61	266.8	181.8	85.0 (mean 85.78)
BaCl ₂ (anhy- drous)	0.02164	1.172	73.01	22.112	55.03	212.5	105.4	107.2
Ba(NO ₃) ₂ (temp., 60°)	0.01240	1.138	69.44	21.021	53.31	287.0	181.8	105.2 (mean 106.2)

It may be noticed (a) that the parachor of the above mentioned magnesium and strontium salts or the two metals has not been previously determined on account of the difficulty of fusing them at high temperature.

(b) That in the case of Ba(NO₃)₂, the salt not being sufficiently soluble at the temperature of 30° to give the required molar fraction for parachor determination, the surface tension and specific gravity have been determined at 60° at which temperature the solubility of this salt is sufficiently high.

(c) That the slightly divergent values obtained with different molar fractions of the strontium salts are due to slight changes in the volume that take place when different quantities of the salts are dissolved in the same quantity of water.

(d) That the mean parachor value of magnesium atom is deduced to be 57.7 and that of strontium as 85.

The parachor of barium calculated from the surface tension and density data of fused BaCl_2 obtained by Motylewski (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, 38, 410) is found to be 106. Sugden ("Parachor and Valency", p. 117) has regarded this figure as a rough value in error by ± 10 units. The parachor of barium deduced from its salts (Table I) is found to be 106.2, and as this figure is confirmed from Motylewski's data, it may reasonably be taken as the more probable value of the parachor of barium atom.

In Table II below, are given the data of atomic numbers and parachors of the elements of group II and also the log values of the constants. In the table below are given the data for the two graphs.

TABLE II.

Element.	Symbol.	Atomic No. =X.	Parachor=Y.	Log X.	Log Y.
Beryllium (Sugden, "Parachor and Valency", p. 145)	Be	4	37.8	0.6021	1.5775
Magnesium	Mg	12	57.7	1.0792	1.7612
Calcium (Motylewski, <i>loc. cit.</i> Sugden, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	Ca	20	68	1.3010	1.8325
Strontium	Sr	38	85	1.5798	1.9294
Barium	Ba	56	106	1.7482	2.0253
Radium	Ra	88	140	1.9445	2.146
			(value deduced from the curve)		(value read on the curve)

FIG. 1a.

FIG. 1b.

The curve in Fig. 1a is obtained when the parachor of each element is plotted against its atomic number, and the curve in Fig. 1b, which is a straight line, is obtained when the log values of the two constants are plotted. When the straight line is extrapolated, the parachor of radium comes to be 140. As mentioned above, there is no direct means available at present for ascertaining the value experimentally. But it is clear from the straight line curve (Fig. 1b), that the log atomic number—log parachor relationship holds in the case of alkaline earth metals and that the parachor is intimately connected to the fundamental property of the atom and the atomic number. Consequently not only the values of atomic parachor of magnesium, strontium, and barium computed from their salts may be taken as reasonably correct but that it is also justifiable to deduce the parachor of radium in the manner it has been done.

CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
D. J. SIND COLLEGE, KARACHI.

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